

A CASE REPORT ON THE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS
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ABSTRACT

Prameha is defined as increased frequency and altered turbidity of urine. According to *Ayurveda*, *Prameha* is considered as one among the *Mahagada*. *Prameha* can be correlated with diabetes mellitus based on signs and symptoms. *Prameha* is *shleshma pradhana tridoshaja vyadhi*. It can be divided into three types based on *doshik* predominance which is also subdivided into further types they are *Kaphaja* into 10 types, *Pittaja* into 6 types, *Vataja* into 4 types which is also *Avasthanusara bheda* of this *vyadhi*. Based on the *chikitsa* aspect it can be also classified as *sthoala prameha* and *Krushna pramehi*. Here is a single case study representing the role of *Ayurveda* in management of Diabetes Mellitus Type II. A 60 years old Indian male came for consultation in OPD of SMBT *Ayurved Hospital* for complaints of *Swedaadhikya*, *Dourbalya*, *Bahumutrata*, *kaphshthivan*, *malavasthambh swaskasthata*, since last 3 months; for which various combination of herbal formulations was given. Maximum improvement was noticed at the end of the treatment after 14 days.

KEYWORDS: *Prameha*, Diabetes Mellitus Type II, BSL F, BSL PP, *Ayurveda*.

INTRODUCTION

Prameha which is said to be a *santarapanajanya vyadhi*^[1] is chronic metabolic disorder. In *ayurvedic* texts *vata*, *pitta* and *kapha* all this three *doshas* are involved in the pathogenesis of *prameha* but *Bahudrava shleshma* is predominant in this disease.^[2] Along with *vata*, *pitta* and *kapha doshas Meda*, *Mamsa*, *Shukra*, *kleda*, *Shonit*, *Vasa*, *Majja*, *Lasika*, *Rasa*, *Ojas*.^[3] this 10 *dushyas* are also involved in the pathogenesis of *prameha*.

Acharya charka in *chikitsasthana* have mentioned that sedentary lifestyle, excess sleep, curds, soup made from meat of domesticated and aquatic animals and animals inhabiting marshy land, milk and its preparations, freshly harvested food articles, freshly prepared drinks, preparations of jaggery and all *Kapha* aggravating factors are responsible for the causation of *prameha*.^[4] *Prameha* is classified into three types and again subdivides.

Clinical features of *prameha* correlates with diabetes mellitus. Diabetes mellitus contributes significant burden to the global population as it is leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. It is chronic, metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose which leads to serious damage to the heart, blood vessel, eyes, kidneys, nerves. Most common type observed among all the patients of DM is type II.^[5]

Despite medical advancements, finding effective diabetes management strategies without side-effects remains challenging. *Ayurveda*, with its holistic approach, offers a promising avenue for managing diabetes and promoting long-term health without harmful side-effects.

Presenting Complaints

A 60-year-old Indian male came for consultation in Out patient department of SMBT *Ayurved Hospital* for complaints of as mentioned above. He was having

history of Diabetes Mellitus type II since last 8 years. No history of any comorbidities noted. Presently, he came to SMBT Ayurved Hospital for further treatment of Prameha.

Clinical Findings

The patient was having complaints of as mentioned above since last 3 months. On examining the patient it was found that pulse was 80/min, blood pressure was

120/ 70 mm Hg. He had *manda agni, kosha krura, jivha sama*. Patient was having *kaphavataj prakriti* with *madhyama sara, shamhan, madhyama, praman* height 165, *satyma madhyam, satva madhyama, ahara shakti & jaran shakti Madhyama*, with *mutravaha malavaha medovaha strotastodushti*. His HbA1c level was 10.0% (6/1/2025) and BSL F -154.4 mg/dl and BSL PP – 188.2 mg/dl (9/01/2025).

Treatment & Outcome

- Good result was observed on reducing the symptoms.

DATE	CLINICAL FINDINGS	TREATMENT
08/01/2025	c/o – - Bahumutrata ++ - Svedaadhikya (sweating) ++ - Dourbalya (weakness) ++ - Kaphshthivan (cough) ++ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea)++ - Malavsthambh(constipation)++	1. Triphala guggul 2 TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5gm BD After meal with warm water.
	o/e – - Bp – 140/ 90 mm Hg - P – 74/ min	3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5gm BD With meal with ghee 4. lodharasava 10ml BD After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1 BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1 OD
09/01/2025	c/o – - Bahumutrata ++ - Svedaadhikya (sweating) ++ - Dourbalya (weakness) ++ - Kaphshthivan (cough) ++ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea)++ Malavsthambh(constipation) ++ o/e – - Bp – 120/70 mm Hg - P – 78/ min	1. Triphala guggul 2 TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5gm BD After meal with warm Water. 3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5gm BD With meal with ghee 4. lodharasava 10ml BD After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1 OD BSL F – 154.4 mg/dl BSL PP – 188.2 mg/dl
10/01/2025	c/o – - Bahumutrata ++ - Svedaadhikya (sweating) ++ - Dourbalya (weakness) ++ - Kaphshthivan (cough) ↓ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea)+ - Malavsthambh (constipation) ++	1. Triphala guggul 2TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5 gm After meal with warm water. 3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5gm BD With meal with ghee
	o/e – - Bp – 160/90 mm Hg - P – 70/ min	4. Lodharasava 10ml BD After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1 BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1 OD 8. Sarvanga snehan with til tail

<p>11/01/2025 TO 13/01/2025</p>	<p>c/o – - Bahumutrata ++ - Svedaadhikya (sweating) ++ - Dourbalya (weakness) + - Kaphshthivan (cough) ↓ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea) ↓ - Malavsthambh (constipation)+</p> <p>o/e – Bp – 160/90 mm Hg P – 70/ min</p>	<p>9. Sewdan with dashmool kwath</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Triphala guggul 2TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5 gm After meal with warm water. 3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5gm BD With meal with ghee 4. Lodharasava 10ml BD After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1 BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1 OD 8. Sarvanga snehan with til tail 9. Sewdan with dashmool kwath
<p>14/01/2025 TO 20/01/2025</p>	<p>c/o – - Bahumutrata ++ - Svedaadhikya (sweating) + - Dourbalya (weakness) + - Kaphshthivan (cough) ↓ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea) ↓ - Malavsthambh (constipation) ↓</p> <p>o/e – - Bp – 180/100 mm Hg - P – 84/ min</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Triphala guggul 2TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5 gm After meal with warm water. 3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5 gm With meal with ghee 4. Lodharasava 10ml BD After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1 OD Sarvanga snehan with til tail 9. Sewdan with dashmool kwath 10. Niruha basti with dashmool kwath And Matra basti with til tail on alternate day.
<p>21/01/2025</p>	<p>c/o – - Bahumutrata + - Svedaadhikya (sweating) ↓ - Dourbalya (weakness) ↓ - Kaphshthivan (cough) ↓ - Shwaskasthata (dyspnea) ↓ - Malavsthambh (constipation) ↓</p> <p>o/e – - Bp – 150/80 mm Hg - P – 72/ min</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Triphala guggul 2TDS After meal with warm water 2. Guduchi – each 1 gm Amalaki – each 1 gm Gokshur – each 1 gm Shankhbhasma – 500 mg each 5gm After meal with warm water. 3. Lavanbhaskar churna - each 3 gm Yashtimadhu churna each 1 gm Haritaki churna each 1 gm 5gm With meal with ghee 4. Lodharasava 10ml After meal with warm water 5. Gandharva haritaki churna 3 gm at night with warm water. 6. Tab. Glz plus (BBF) 1BD 7. Tab. Ondero met 25/500 1OD 8. Sarvanga snehan with til tail 9. Sewdan with dashmool kwath

Follow Up

- Good result was observed on reducing the symptoms.
- Hematological parameter was reinvestigated on 06/01/2025 at this time HbA1c level was 10.0% and

BSL F -154.4 mg/dl and BSL PP – 188.2 mg/dl on 9/01/2025 which was reduced and BSL F -97.4 mg/dl and BSL PP – 173.5 mg/dl on 18/01/2025.

Test	Before treatment	After treatment
BSLF	154mg/dl	97mg/dl
BSL PP	188mg/dl	173mg/dl

DISCUSSION

स्थूलः प्रमेही बलवानिहैकः कृशस्तथैकः परि दुबलश्चा संबृहणं तत्र कृशस्य कार्यं संशोधं दोषबलानधकर्या^[6]

According to *charak, prameha chikitsa* is based on the aspect of *sthoola pramehi* and *Krushn pramehi rugna*. For the *krushn pramehi rugna*, nourishment is necessary, while for *sthoola pramehi rugna*, purification is necessary.

Triphala guggulu ^[7]	Triphala Guggulu constituents contain <i>Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura Rasa, Ushna Virya, Katu Vipaka, Laghu, Ruksha, Ushna, Tikshna Gunas, Tridosahara</i> ^[8] Triphala-the three myrobalans (<i>Terminalia chebula, Terminalia bellirica, Emblica officinalis</i>) is a suggestive combination that possesses hypoglycaemic qualities ^[9] it nourish the <i>rasa dhatu</i> and purify and regulate the <i>rakta dhatu</i> which is responsible for the transport of glucose and strengthen the <i>mamsa dhatu</i> . It also regulates the <i>jatharagni</i> and <i>dhatvagni</i> . It is a safe and effective <i>ayurvedic</i> formulation for management of <i>prameha</i> . Its unique combination of herbs works synergistically to improve insulin sensitivity, regulate glucose metabolism, and reduce inflammation and oxidative stress. ^[10]
Guduchi, Amalaki and Gokshura	Guduchi, amalaki and gokshura has <i>rasayana</i> property. Guduchi has antidiabetic property. ^[11] It balances all three <i>doshas</i> and helps to regulate blood sugar levels. Also amalaki has a antidiabetic property. ^[12]
Lodhrasava ^[13]	Lodhrasava has a anti-diabetic property ^[14] Lodhrasava helps to strengthen the <i>mutravaha strotas</i> and nourish the kidney and reduces frequency and urgency of urination.
Lavanbhaskar churna	Lavanbhaskar churna regulates the <i>jatharagni</i> by its <i>Tikshna guna</i> . It has <i>deepan panchan</i> properties. Also balances <i>vata</i> and <i>kapha dosas</i> Lavan (Salt) acts as a catalyst during the digestive process and provides lubrication and helps soften food and make it easily digestible and reduce the constipation. ^[15]
Gandharva haritaki	Haritaki also acts as a <i>Anuloman</i> and <i>tridosahara</i> . Gandharva haritaki has purgative and laxative action ^[16]

A patient has been treated with *Ayurvedic* treatment as described above. And Good result was observed on reducing the symptoms and Hematological parameter.

CONCLUSION

From the present study, it is concluded that in spite of high blood sugar levels, we could successfully manage the patient with *ayurvedic* medicines.

With an FBS level of 154 mg/ dl and PP2BS level of 188 mg/ dl, the patient had type 2 diabetes that had not been well controlled by allopathic treatment. After 14 days of treatment, the symptoms was reduced and the sugar level was found to be under control after prescribed the *ayurvedic* medicines. FBS level of 97 mg/ dl and PP2BS level of 173 mg/ dl.

Several more such case study reports are required to analyze the effectiveness of *ayurvedic* intervention for diabetes management.

REFERENCES

1. Vidhyadhara Shukla, Ravidatta Tripathi. Charaka Samhita of Acharya Charaka. Reprint edition. Varanasi; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, 2006; 317p.
2. Vidhyadhara Shukla, Ravidatta Tripathi. Charaka Samhita of Acharya Charaka. Reprint edition. Varanasi; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, 2006; 503p.
3. Vidhyadhara Shukla, Ravidatta Tripathi. Charaka Samhita of Acharya Charaka. Reprint edition. Varanasi; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, 2006; 167p.
4. Vidhyadhara Shukla, Ravidatta Tripathi. Charaka Samhita of Acharya Charaka. Reprint edition. Varanasi; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, 2006; 169p.
5. Harsh Mohan. Textbook of pathology. 6th edition. New delhi. Jaypee brother medical Publisher private limited, 2010; 819p.
6. Charak Samhita Bhag 2, by Vaidya Vijay Shankar Kale, reprint, 2016; Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, Chikitsa Sthan, Adhyay no.06, Shloka no. 15, Page no.167.
7. BhavPrakasha nighantu, guggulu varg, Verse 24-25.
8. Neelam Rawat, Shuchi Mitra, Usha Sharma, Khem Chand Sharma. An overview of Triphala Guggulu and its ingredients. AYUSHDHARA, 2023; 10(Suppl 1): 47-59.
9. Sowmya. S. Rajan and Seema Anatomy, ‘‘Hypoglycemic effects of triphala on selected non – insulin dependent Diabetes mellitus subjects’’, Ancient Science of life, March 2008; Volume 17(3): 45-49.
10. Neelam Rawat, Shuchi Mitra, Usha Sharma, Khem Chand Sharma. An overview of Triphala Guggulu and its ingredients. AYUSHDHARA, 2023; 10(Suppl 1): 47-59.
11. Sharma R, Kumar V, Ashok BK, Galib R, Prajapati

- PK, Ravishankar B. Hypoglycemic and anti-hyperglycemic activity of Guduchi Satva in experimental animals. *Ayu*, 2013 Oct; 34(4): 417-20.
12. Akhtar MS, Ramzan M, Ali A, Ahmad M. Effect of Amla fruit (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn.) on blood glucose and lipid profile of normal subjects and type 2 diabetic patients. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*, 2011; 62(6): 609-16.
 13. Bhavaprakasha Nighantu. (16th century CE). *Haritakyadi Varga*. Verse 157-158. Translated by Gyanendra Pandey. Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Varanasi.
 14. Butala MA, Kukkupuni SK, Vishnuprasad CN. Ayurvedic anti-diabetic formulation Lodhrasavam inhibits alpha-amylase, alpha-glucosidase and suppresses adipogenic activity in vitro. *J Ayurveda Integr Med*, 2017 Jul-Sep; 8(3): 145-151.
 15. Punam Kumari et al: Lavana Bhaskar Churna – An Ayurvedic Formulation Used In The Treatment Of Gastric Intestinal Disease: A Review. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal*, 2022.
 16. <https://www.bimbima.com/ayurveda/gandharva-haritaki-churna-benefits-ingredients- dosage/466>.